

Using Networked Ontologies to Support the Development of Software Systems with Adaptive User Interface

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Supplementary Material

Context: New ways of interacting with computers, smartphones, and other devices have brought new challenges, such as the need to ensure that different types of users can easily use the same system. Adaptive User Interface (AUI) systems have been recognized as a solution to this matter. **Objective:** This exploratory study aimed to show that using ontologies from an ontology network to develop an AUI system is useful and feasible. **Method:** The HCI-ON, an ontology that represents concepts related to human-computer interaction (HCI), was used to develop an AUI system called SNOPI. An interview was conducted with the developer of SNOPI to obtain feedback on the use of HCI-ON in creating the system. From this experience, the first version of an ontology-based process to guide the development of AUI systems emerged. **Results:** The study showed that the ontology was useful at the conceptual level by serving as a basis to define the system's structural model and at the operational level by providing semantics used in a reasoning engine to adapt the UI at run-time. Additionally, it was possible to create an ontology-based process to guide the development of AUI systems. **Conclusion:** The use of networked ontologies can be a useful and feasible approach to support the development of AUI systems. The ontology-based process created from this experience can be used as a guide for future developers of AUI systems.

This package contains supplementary material of the study performed:

- i. The questionnaire used to collect data (Google Forms format) – (available at <https://forms.gle/FNXa5W6YBcoMrXKi8>)
- ii. The consent form (pdf format)
- iii. The questionnaire used to collect data (pdf format)
- iv. Developer interview questions about SNOPI development (pdf format)
- v. The file containing the SNOPI system source code and database file (zip format)
- vi. The file of the operational ontology used in the SNOPI system (owl format)